

BIOCHEMICAL ASPECTS OF DEVELOPMENT AND PROGRESSION OF DIABETES MELLITUS: MECHANISMS OF HYPERGLYCEMIA AND THEIR IMPACT ON THE BODY

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Abstract. *This article provides an overview of the biochemical mechanisms underlying the development of diabetes mellitus, including a detailed review of symptoms, causes and risk factors. Current strategies for diagnosis, treatment and prevention of this disease are discussed. It is noted that a healthy lifestyle plays a key role in the maintenance of diabetes mellitus, emphasizing the importance of a comprehensive approach to the management of this disease.*

Keywords: *diabetes mellitus, gestational diabetes mellitus, GLUT transporters, hyperglycemia.*

INTRODUCTION

Diabetes mellitus is a chronic disease that is becoming increasingly common and poses a serious threat to public health. According to the World Health Organization, more than 400 million people worldwide suffer from diabetes, and this number continues to increase. Diabetes is one of the main causes of cardiovascular diseases, stroke, kidney failure and blindness.

Biochemical studies show that the main mechanism of diabetes development is impaired glucose metabolism and insulin resistance. Insufficient insulin secretion or impaired insulin action leads to an increase in blood glucose levels, which in turn can lead to various complications.

According to the World Health Organization:

- About 422 million people worldwide suffer from diabetes.
- The prevalence of diabetes among people over 18 years of age increased from 4.7% in 1980 to 8.5% in 2014.
- In 2014, diabetes caused 1.5 million deaths, with 48% of all diabetes-related deaths occurring in people under 70 years of age.
- An additional 460,000 deaths were due to diabetes-related kidney disease, and elevated blood glucose levels account for about 20% of cardiovascular deaths.
- The age-standardized death rate from diabetes increased by 3% between 2000 and 2019, and by 13% in lower-middle-income countries.
- Diabetes is a leading cause of blindness, kidney failure, heart attacks, strokes, and lower-limb amputations.
- Almost 50% of deaths due to high blood glucose occur before age 70.[1]

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Diabetes is a metabolic disease characterized by impaired carbohydrate metabolism and hyperglycemia. The main cause is impaired interaction between tissues and insulin. Glucose plays a key role as the main source of energy for the body, and its deficiency in tissues, as well as insufficient accumulation in the liver as glycogen, lead to an increase in blood glucose levels, which is characterized as diabetes. The development of the disease is facilitated by various factors,

such as pheochromocytoma, adrenal hyperactivity, hyperthyroidism, impaired sensitivity to carbohydrates and transient hyperglycemia. In some cases, secondary diabetes occurs, which may disappear when the main factor is eliminated, but long-term exposure to these factors can lead to primary diabetes.

The longer hyperglycemia continues, the more severe the disease becomes. This is due to the mechanisms that the body uses to reduce blood glucose levels, including the storage of glucose in fats, glycolysis of the cell membrane and the activation of the sorbitol-glucose splitting function. These processes can lead to the formation of toxins, damage to nerve cells and damage to blood vessels. The gradual progression of protein glycosylation and cholesterol accumulation can lead to the development of microangiopathy, which can ultimately lead to damage to virtually all organs.[2]

TYPES OF DIABETES MELLITUS

In 1936, Sir Harold Percival Himsworth published a study that for the first time identified two types of diabetes as separate diseases. This marked a new stage in the understanding of diabetes, dividing it into two types: with absolute insulin deficiency (type 1) and with relative insulin deficiency (type 2). This led to diabetes being considered as a syndrome that could occur with either type 1 or type 2 diabetes.

The term "type 1 diabetes mellitus" is used to describe a group of diseases that develop due to the gradual destruction of beta cells in the pancreas, leading to a deficiency in proinsulin synthesis and hyperglycemia, requiring hormone replacement therapy. "Type 2 diabetes mellitus" is characterized by its development in people with excess accumulation of adipose tissue, which leads to insulin resistance, excessive synthesis of proinsulin, insulin and amylin by the beta cells of the pancreas, causing a "relative deficiency".

The prevalence of diabetes mellitus varies depending on ethnicity. Among people of Asian race over 40 years in the UK, type 2 diabetes mellitus is most common - 20%, while in people of black race this figure is 17%. There is also a different incidence of complications. People of Asian race have an increased risk of developing diabetic nephropathy and ischemic heart disease, but a reduced risk of diabetic foot syndrome. People of black race are more likely to have severe arterial hypertension and more often develop gestational diabetes mellitus.

Gestational diabetes mellitus is a pathological condition characterized by hyperglycemia in some women during pregnancy, which usually resolves after delivery. The causes are not fully understood, but it is thought that HLA antigens, especially HLA DR2, 3, and 4, may play a role. It is also thought that excess proinsulin and high concentrations of hormones such as progesterone, cortisol, prolactin, human placental lactogen, and estrogen may affect beta-cell function and insulin sensitivity.

BIOCHEMISTRY OF DIABETES MELLITUS.

Phosphorylation of enzymes can change their activity - they can be activated or inactive. Kinases phosphorylate, and phosphatases dephosphorylate.

For example, insulin antagonists such as glucagon and epinephrine activate protein kinase A through a cascade mechanism, which phosphorylates the enzyme glycogen phosphorylase, which leads to its activation.

The insulin receptor, which has tyrosine kinase activity, does not require second messengers. It phosphorylates tyrosine residues, which activates phosphatases that inhibit glycogen phosphorylase and activates glycogen synthase.

GLUT-2, present in the liver and β -cells of the pancreas, plays a key role in regulating glucose levels in the body. It is important to note that GLUT-2, like glucokinase, has a low affinity for glucose, meaning that they require more glucose to function.

When blood glucose levels rise, a reaction occurs to reduce these levels. The influx of glucose stimulates the formation of ATP, which in turn opens calcium channels. Increased calcium levels in the cell stimulate the release of insulin.

GLUT-2 and glucokinase, having a lower affinity for glucose, act as "hyperglycemia sensors", responding to changes in blood glucose levels and initiating appropriate biochemical processes to maintain glucose homeostasis in the body.

GLUT-4, which is dormant in the cell, moves to the cell surface when exposed to insulin. Its movement can also be stimulated by muscle contractions.[4]

Increased blood glucose levels can lead to glycosylation of HbA, forming HbA1C, which indicates previous hyperglycemia. Decreased glucokinase affinity can lead to insufficient insulin production even at high glucose levels. Congenital type 2 diabetes mellitus - MODY (maturity onset diabetes of the young) - is associated with this process.

SYMPTOMS AND DIAGNOSIS.

Symptoms of diabetes mellitus are most often related to elevated blood glucose levels. In the early stages of the disease, mild hyperglycemia is often asymptomatic, making diagnosis difficult, especially if regular testing is not performed. More severe hyperglycemia causes glucose to appear in the urine and an increase in the frequency of urination due to osmotic diuresis. This can lead to polyuria and polydipsia, which can ultimately cause orthostatic hypotension and dehydration. Dehydration can manifest as weakness, fatigue, and mood changes, with symptoms coming and going with fluctuations in blood glucose levels.

Hyperglycemia is sometimes accompanied by excessive appetite, but this is usually not the main symptom. Weight loss, nausea, vomiting, changes in vision, and increased susceptibility to infections may also occur. Patients with type 1 diabetes often seek medical attention with symptoms of hyperglycemia, sometimes with manifestations of diabetic ketoacidosis.

With type 2 diabetes, symptoms can be so mild that the disease is detected only during a routine examination. In some cases, the first manifestation of diabetes can be a hyperosmolar hyperglycemic state that develops during stress or when taking certain medications that aggravate glucose metabolism disorders, such as corticosteroids.

Various methods are used to confirm the diagnosis of diabetes, including fasting blood glucose levels, glycosylated hemoglobin (HbA1C) analysis, and sometimes an oral glucose tolerance test. Often, the diagnosis is established during screening.

There is also an invention created to diagnose a predisposition to type 2 diabetes in the early stages. To conduct the diagnosis, the open palms of both hands are scanned in combination with the fingers. The obtained images allow to evaluate dermatoglyphic features characterizing the topography of palmar patterns and patterns of distal phalanges of fingers. During the analysis various parameters are taken into account, such as the type of the obtained pattern; the direction to the palmar fields, which have the main palmar lines A, B, C and D; the ridge count and the value of the angle α ; the type of patterns on the thenar, hypothenar, in the interdigital fields and on the fingers; the width, number and nature of the arrangement of palmar lines; the arrangement of axial and palmar triradii. Based on these data, a conclusion is made about the probability of developing type 2 diabetes. This invention can be used for medical prevention and determining the risk group,

that is, for screening people who do not yet have the disease, but the risk of developing type 2 diabetes exists.[3]

MAIN CAUSES OF DEATH IN DM.

As noted in most studies, the main cause of death in patients with DM II is, first of all, cardiovascular pathology. However, in recent years, there has been an increase in deaths from infectious diseases of the respiratory and genitourinary organs accompanying DM II, as well as malignant neoplasms, the occurrence of which is also associated with the side effects of antidiabetic drugs.

Existing risk factors for death today include non-specific ones, such as age, gender, physical inactivity, nutritional culture, bad habits, lipid metabolism disorders and high blood pressure.

Specific factors for DM include factors associated with the duration and severity of the disease, blood glucose levels and hypoglycemia, as well as the period from the onset of the disease. Women with gestational diabetes are potential patients with type I or II diabetes in the subsequent period of life.

Projections of the overall consequences of diabetes over the next decades show that damage and risk of developing diseases of the heart, blood vessels, eyes, kidneys and nerves will increase even more rapidly over time. Diabetic retinopathy may be responsible for 1% of global cases of blindness. Diabetes is one of the leading causes of kidney failure. It is known that the overall risk of death among people with diabetes is at least 2 times higher than the risk of death among people of the same age who do not have diabetes. Identification of risk factors for death in diabetes is necessary in order to develop measures to prevent high and early mortality, as well as to increase the duration of remissions and prevent the development of complications in diabetes II.I

CONCLUSION

Diabetes mellitus is a serious disease that requires constant attention and self-monitoring. Patients with diabetes should be aware of their disease, monitor their blood glucose levels, maintain a healthy lifestyle, and communicate regularly with their doctor.

Prevention of diabetes complications plays a key role in maintaining the health of patients. Regular medical examinations, blood pressure and cholesterol control, foot care, giving up bad habits, and maintaining a healthy lifestyle will help prevent the development of complications.

It is important to remember that diabetes is not a proposition, but a challenge that can be accepted and successfully overcome with the right approach to treatment and support from others. Self-management of the disease, education, and understanding of their condition will help patients with diabetes live a full life and maintain a high quality of life.

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